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ADAMANTANE-1-CARBOXYLIC ACID AS A THIONECARBOXYLIC ACID SYNTHON

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Abstract

Adamantane-1-carboxylic acid (AdCOOH) is an important chemical compound that can be used in the fields of science and industry. The purpose of the work was a detailed study of adamantane-1-carboxylic acid, its chemical properties and reactivity, in the context of the development of new derivatives. The reaction of adamantane-1-carboxylic acid methyl ester with phosphorus pentasulfide in dimethoxyethane or dioxane was the first to produce adamantane-1-thioncarboxylic acid methyl ester. Its reactions with hydroxylamine and O-methylhydroxylamine lead to the predominant formation of 1-adamantyl cyanide and 1-adamantyl isocyanate, respectively. The reaction products of the thionester with piperidine are thiolester and the piperidinium salt of adamantane-1-thiolcarboxylic acid, the formation of which is accompanied by N-alkylation of the amine. The reaction of the thionester with diazomethane produces adamantyl-containing thiadiazoles and thiadiazolines.

Keywords: adamantane-1-carboxylic acid methyl ester, phosphorus pentasulfide, adamantane-1-thioncarboxylic acid methyl ester, adamantyl-containing thiadiazoles and thiadiazolines.

Introduction.

Adamantane-1-carboxylic acid (AdCOOH) has attracted considerable attention of scientists due to its special characteristics and possible applications in various fields of chemistry. Adamantane-1-carboxylic acid is used to prepare various adamantane derivatives and is known for its ability to form complex compounds with a variety of metals, including dimetallic clusters and coordination polymers. The obtained compounds were subjected to structural analysis using various methods, including IR, ^1H and ^{13}C nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR). Some of these substances were studied using X-ray structural analysis, which provided an opportunity to obtain significant information about their molecular structure and conformation.

O. Velichko and others. developed a technique for the synthesis of complexes of 1-adamantanecarboxylic acid with metals. As part of the study, the spectral and thermal properties of the obtained complex compounds were studied in detail [1]. Adamantane-1-carboxylic acid has been shown to interact with various metals, such as rhenium, iron, copper, and others, forming stable complexes. Complex compounds with 1-adamantyl carboxylate and 1-adamantyl acetate were synthesized and characterized by ultraviolet spectroscopy by A.V. Shtemenko and others. [2]. Using the X-ray diffraction method, the structure of the solvate of the adamantyl

carboxylate compound with rhenium was established. Such complexes were investigated in the context of anticancer activity by N. Shtemenko et al. [3]. Reaction complexes of diarenium(III) with cis- and trans-diadamantyl carboxylate acids were found to have similar antitumor activity, with a slight advantage in the case of the cis analogue. As a result, the difference in the mechanisms of anticancer action of these compounds was established, which consists in the formation of monofunctional adducts and subsequent cross-linking and formation of cross-links between proteins and DNA. The anti-radical and DNA-binding properties of the studied substances were also considered. These findings indicate the potential effectiveness of using these complexes in the treatment of cancer. However, in dierenium clusters, the gradual replacement of halide ligands with carboxylates leads to a decrease in the reaction rate, as noted by A. Shtemenko et al. [4]. However, it is also indicated that there are prospects for use in medicinal preparations due to low toxicity and anti-radical properties arising from the δ -component of the electronic transition of the quadruple Re-Re bond. Another feature of AdCOOH is its ability to coordinate polymerization, which was reviewed in detail by I. Antonyuk [5]. The paper presented the synthesis of new (PEG, Ada)-grafted dextran obtained by azide-alkyne cycloaddition catalyzed by Cu(I), with a high degree of

substitution by PEG and Ad groups. It was found that the affinity of these polymers to monomeric β CD and their ability to form surface layers with β -cyclodextrin polymers strongly depend on the degree of Ad substitution. Using Ad-modified dextrans, the resulting microgels can be physically cross-linked to obtain hierarchical 3D hydrogels with a gel-sol transition temperature in the physiological range.

On the basis of obtaining the results of the synthesis of similar acidic acids, adamantane-1-carboxylic acid is supplemented with a reactive acidic acid. Among these, 1-aminoadamantane hydrochloride is also easily synthesized, which is an antiviral drug and is used to fight infections caused by influenza A [7]. The statistics have a great emphasis on the likes of adamantane. Zokrem, with the help of differential scanning calorimetry, enthalpy, melting point and heat capacity of the solid phase were removed [8]. The findings in the robot are correlated with the powerful chemical characteristics of adamantane-1-carboxylic acid, which were helixed and under constant investigation. During subsequent syntheses, similar acids can be solidified by reaction, so that adamantane-1-carboxylic acid readily undergoes condensation/cyclization reactions. This is confirmed by the work of M. Soseliya et al., which indicated that a series of similar acids were synthesized through the direct condensation of adamantane carboxylic acid with methyl 3,4-diaminobenzoate from trimethylsilyl polyphosphate [9].

One of the important findings is that 1-adamantanecarboxylic acid can create mononuclear tris(carboxylate) coordination complexes with various transition metals, such as Mn, Ni, Co and Zn. This is confirmed by various scientific evidence. For example, according to the statistics of D. Lita in. Photoreactive complexes in a discrete form were investigated, including 4-stilbazole and 1-carboxyadamantane [10]. Based on the results, studies with zinc(II) showed photoinertness; however, when zinc(II) was substituted with honey(II), the complexed compound exhibited a slight photoreaction through photoinduction similar to cyclobutene.

Work by J. Wang Ta in. is directed at the understanding of authorities and the accumulation of α -/ β -/ γ -cyclodextrins (CDs) and the like in drug delivery systems [11]. The inclusion of β -CD with various simple and bioconjugated adamantane-like compounds was investigated and it was found that all six compounds created inclusion adducts. The focus is directly on the creation of complexes of the "guest-guest" type with vicistrans similar to adamantane, which will take place of biologically active groups. Article by K. Jita in. It also confirms the creation of supramolecular complexes through the release of 1,3,4-oxadiazole, functionalized with adamantane [12]. Such scientific results will be useful for further investigation of the creation of the "master-guest" complexes and in the context of further developments of this work. For example, in the work of H. Yoshiky and in. a study was made of vikorstan photochemically stable sums, as well as the adduct of 1-adamantanecarboxylic acid, glycidyl methacrylate (AdC-GMA) and vikristan for the preparation of smelt from polymethacrylate mesh (CAP), which

mixed cycle blocks odextrin-adamantane-gospodar-gist [13].

The details of the recognition of various monocarboxylic acids with the help of a group of substituted imidazoles, which include a pyridyl fragment, have been studied. Work by S. Prajapati et al. examines the influx of substitutes and the release of "nitrogen" from the peridine part of the receptors during the recognition process [14]. The most effective recognition is prevented if the receptor contains a 2-pyridyl fragment. Imidazoles with a 3-pyridyl layer demonstrate weak binding properties, similar to phenyl-substituted imidazoles. The size of monocarboxylic acids is also important for the creation of "gospodar-gist" complexes. The characteristics of adamantane-like ligands were obtained from the article by V. Slyusarchuk, which is a reliable introduction to a complete description of the properties of adamantane-1-carboxylic acid [15]. The results may be used as a source for future scientific research.

Although this work did not examine the biological activity of similar adamantane-1-carboxylic acids, this aspect can clearly be considered through their potential importance in biological applications. Adamantane-1-carboxylic acid compounds are characterized by a variety of potential biological properties that provide not only antiviral, antibacterial and antifungal properties, but also the ability to provide in medicinal applications and in cancer treatment [16]. Similar adamantane-1-carboxylic acids, such as amantadine and others, are known to have antiviral activity. They are likely to stagnate in patients infected with influenza virus type A. In addition, studies have shown their potential effectiveness in combating other illnesses caused by viruses, such as viral hepatitis Other respiratory viruses [17]. Various modifications of adamantane-1-carboxylic acid potentially exhibit antibacterial activity [18]. Knowledge about this may be useful in the treatment of bacterial infections, which are becoming increasingly important for the use of essential antibiotics. For example, the robot studied in detail the action of similar acids in the fight against tuberculosis. Based on further studies, the most potent indolamides based on adamantanol/adamantane 8j/8k showed increased effectiveness against extensive strains of M. tuberculosis with minimal values and inhibitory concentration. Studies of indole-2-carboxamide, which replace adamantanol, have shown an immediate difference in water and silicon, as well as experimentally compared with adamantane analogues [19]. It is noted that the antimycobacterial and physical-chemical profiles of these compounds confirm the findings that the adamantane component is a suitable replacement for the adamantane framework in the indol-2-carboxamide series Some MmpL3 inhibitors.

Research has shown that adamantane-1-carboxylic acid and related compounds may have antifungal activity against various types of fungi, including candidiasis and other fungal infections. Among them are new studies on the development of antimicrobial peptides. In this study, N- and C-modified biomolecular peptide analogues of VV-hemorphin-5 and VV-hemorphin-7 were synthesized to replace different amino acids, 1-adamantanecarboxylic acid and qin.

This compound was synthesized by solid-phase peptide synthesis and assessed in aqueous solutions at different pH values using spectroscopic and electrochemical methods [20]. It has been revealed that they exhibit interaction between light and electricity, preserving structural and conformational integrity in components. New research methods have been used to modify textile materials, and the binding of peptides to the surface of bulk fibers has been confirmed. The antiviral and antimicrobial activity of these compounds has been studied, revealing their effectiveness against various types of viruses and bacteria [21].

It is known that sulfur-containing derivatives of adamantane - thioamides, thiadiazoles - show high antiviral activity [1, 2]. Unexplored adamantyl-containing thionesters could serve as convenient synthons for their synthesis. This work is devoted to the synthesis and study of some chemical properties of the methyl ester of adamantane-1-thioncarboxylic acid (II).

Materials and methods.

IR spectra were obtained on a Specord 751R spectrometer for samples in KBr tablets containing 0.25% of the substance. Or in a thin film, layer thickness 0.6 mm. PMR spectra were taken on Bruker AVANCE III HD (400 MHz). GLC analysis was carried out on a ЦВет-500 device, glass column 2000x3 mm, 15% Apiezon L on Inerton N-AW-HMDS carrier, temperature 150-260°C (10 deg/min), carrier gas - helium (40 ml/min). The mixtures were separated by column chromatography on Silicagel L 40/100 sorbent. Adamantane-1-carboxylic acid was synthesized according to the procedure [23]. P₂S₅ from Aldrich.

Adamantane-1-thioncarboxylic acid methyl ester (2). *a.* 4.44 g of P₄S₁₀ was added to a solution of 1.94 g of adamantane-1-carboxylic acid methyl ester (1) in 20 ml of anhydrous dimethoxyethane. The mixture was boiled with vigorous stirring for 6 hours. The solvent was evaporated in vacuum. The residue - yellow oil - was dissolved in hexane and washed 2 times with a 5% solution of sodium carbonate and water. After drying with sodium sulfate, the solvent was removed in vacuo. Yield 2.1 g of a mixture of compounds containing, according to GLC data, 10% compound (1), 66% compound (2), 24% unidentified compounds. The mixture of substances was passed through a chromatographic column and eluted with hexane. Yield of compound (2) 1.35 g (64%), retention time 792 s.

b. From 1.94 g of ether (1) in 20 ml of anhydrous dioxane, 2 g of a mixture of compounds was obtained, which, according to GLC data, consisted of 11% compound (1), 89% compound (2). After passing through a chromatographic column, the yield of compound (2) was 1.76 g (88%).

5-(1-Adamantyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (3) and 5-(1-adamantyl)-1,2,3-thiadiazole (4). A solution of diazomethane and diethyl ether obtained from 5.85 g of nitrosomethylurea was added to a solution of 2.1 g of thioneether (2) and 20 ml of methanol. The reaction mixture was left in the dark at room temperature for 48 hours. Then 100 ml of ether was added and washed with dilute hydrochloric acid. The organic layer was separated and dried over sodium sulfate. The solvent was removed in vacuo. A mixture of thiadiazoles in an

amount of 2.1 g was passed through a chromatographic column, eluent: hexane-ether, 1:1. We obtained 1.25 g of thionester (2), 0.15 g (7%) of 5-(1-adamantyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (3), 0.7 g (32%) of 5-(1-adamantyl)-1,2,3-thiadiazole (4).

5-(1-Adamantyl)-5-methoxy-1,2,3-thiadiazoline (5) and 1-(1-adamantyl)-1-methoxyethylene (6). A solution of diazomethane in 50 ml of ether, prepared from 5.85 g of nitrosomethylurea, was added to a solution of 2.1 g of thioneether (2) in 20 ml of diethyl ether. The reaction mixture was left in the dark at room temperature for 48 hours. After washing with dilute hydrochloric acid, the ethereal solution was dried with sodium sulfate. The solvent was evaporated. A mixture of reaction products in an amount of 2.4 g was passed through a chromatographic column, eluent: hexane-diethyl ether 5:1. We obtained 0.5 g of a mixture of compounds containing, according to PMR data, 20% of compound (2), 80% of compound (6). Yield of compound (5) 0.55 g (22%).

1-(1-Adamantyl)-1-methoxyethylene (6) from 1-adamantylmethylketone. To a solution of 0.89 g of 1-adamantyl methyl ketone in 25 ml of anhydrous dioxane, 10.6 g of orthoformic ether and 0.1 g of *p*-toluenesulfonic acid were added and boiled for 4.5 hours. The solvent was evaporated in vacuum. The residue (0.96 g) was passed through a chromatographic column, eluent: hexane-diethyl ether 5:1. Yield of compound (6) 0.79 g (83%).

Decomposition of 5-(1-adamantyl)-5-methoxy-1,2,3-thiadiazoline (5). A solution of 0.1 g of compound (5) in 10 ml of a 1:1 mixture of methanol and diethyl ether was boiled for 3 hours. The solvent was evaporated. We obtained 0.09 g of a mixture of substances consisting, according to PMR data, of 75% compound (5) and 25% compound (6).

Reaction of adamantane-1-thioncarboxylic acid methyl ester (2) with hydroxylamine. 0.22 g of sodium metal was added to 30 ml of absolute methanol with ice cooling and stirring. After complete dissolution of sodium, 9.42 g of hydroxylamine hydrochloride was added to the solution. Then, a solution of 1.05 g of thionester (2) in methanol was added dropwise over 2 hours and stirred for another 1 hour. The solvent was evaporated in vacuum at 40°C. Water was added to the residue and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid until neutral according to the universal indicator. The precipitate of **N-hydroxyiminomethyl ester of adamantane-1-carboxylic acid (8)** was filtered off, dried in air, and washed with pentane. Yield 0.3 g (29%). M. p. 130-132°C. NMR spectrum (δ , ppm): 1.5-2.0 (15H), 3.88 (3H), 8.62 (1H). IR spectrum (cm⁻¹): 1670 (C=N), 2800-3000 (CH), 3300 (OH). Found, %: C 69.11; H 9.17; N 6.80. C₁₂H₁₉NO₂. Calculated, %: C 69.20; H 9.19; N 6.73.

The aqueous filtrate was acidified with hydrochloric acid and extracted with diethyl ether. The extract was dried with sodium sulfate. The solvent was evaporated in vacuum. Yield of **1-adamantylisothiocyanate (7)** 0.3 g (71%). M. p. 165-167°C, avg. [14]: 166-168°C. IR spectrum (cm⁻¹): 2100 (NCS), 2800-3000 (CH). Found, %: C 68.32; H 7.85; N 7.21. C₁₁H₁₅NS. Calculated, %: C 68.34; H 7.82; N 7.24.

Hydrolysis of adamantane-1-carboxylic acid N-hydroxyiminomethyl ester (8). 20 ml of 10% Hydrochloric acid was added to 0.1 g of compound (8) and boiled for 2 hours. The precipitate that formed after cooling the reaction mass was filtered off and dried in air. Yield of adamantane-1-carboxylic acid (11) 0.09 g (quantitative). M. p. 178-181°C, average: [15] 180-181°C. Data GLC, retention time, s: 540 (glass column 1000x3 mm, 5% Apiezon L, temperature 150-260°C, 15 deg/min, helium, 40 ml/min). IR spectrum (cm⁻¹): 1680 (C=O), 2800-3000 (CH), 3100 (OH). NMR spectrum (δ, ppm): 1.62 (6H), 1.93 (3H), 9.1 s (1H). Found, %: C 73.28; N 8.91. C₁₁H₁₆O₂. Calculated, %: C 73.30; H 8.95.

Reduction of N-hydroxyiminomethyl ester of adamantane-1-carboxylic acid (8). To a suspension of 0.3 g of LiAlH₄ in 20 ml of absolute diethyl ether, a solution of 0.25 g of compound (8) in 10 ml of ether was slowly added with cooling and stirring. Then boiled for 1 hour. 0.3 ml of water, 0.3 ml of a 15% KOH solution, and 0.9 ml of water were added sequentially to the reaction mass while cooled. The precipitate that formed was filtered off and washed with ether on the filter. The filtrate was dried with KOH. The solvent was evaporated. Yield of **1-adamantylmethylamine (10)** 0.16 g (82%). *n*_D²⁰ 1.453. NMR spectrum (δ, ppm): 0.81 s (2H), 1.40 d (6H), 1.64 d (6H), 1.89 (3H), 2.18 s (2H). IR spectrum of amine hydrochloride (10) (cm⁻¹): 2800-3000 (CH), 3050 (NH₃⁺). Found, %: C 79.92; H 11.55; N 8.44. C₁₁H₁₉N. Calculated, %: C 79.94; H 11.59; N 8.47.

Reaction of adamantane-1-thionecarboxylic acid methyl ester (2) with O-methylhydroxylamine. *a.* 0.22 g of sodium metal was added to 30 ml of absolute methanol with ice cooling and stirring. After complete dissolution of sodium, 0.42 g of O-methylhydroxylamine hydrochloride was added to the solution. Then a solution of 1.05 g of ether (2) in 10 ml of methanol was added and boiled for 13 hours. The solvent was removed in vacuum. Water was added to the residue and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid until neutral according to the universal indicator. Extracted with diethyl ether. The extract was dried with sodium sulfate, and the ether was evaporated in vacuum. The yield of the mixture of compounds is 0.8 g, according to GLC data, 52% compound (2), 48% compound (9). The mixture was washed several times with boiling pentane. The resulting precipitate of adamantane-1-carboxylic acid nitrile (9) was filtered off. Yield 0.37 g (46%). M. p. 190-193°C, compare: [18] 193-196°C (acetone). Retention time (GLC) 558 s. NMR spectrum (δ, ppm): 2.70 (6H), 2.90 (9H). IR spectrum (cm⁻¹): 2250 (CN), 2800-3000 (CH). Found, %: C 81.92; H 9.35; N 8.71. C₁₁H₁₅N. Calculated, %: C 81.94; H 9.38; N 8.69.

b. Similar to experiment *a*, 0.84 g of O-methylhydroxylamine hydrochloride was added to a solution of sodium methoxide (from 0.44 g of Na). We obtained 0.85 g of a mixture of compounds, consisting, according to GLC data, of 9% compound (2) and 91% compound (9).

Reaction of adamantane-1-thionecarboxylic acid methyl ester (2) with piperidine. *a.* 40 ml of piperidine was added to 1.05 g of ether (2) and boiled for

6 hours. Piperidine was removed in vacuo with the addition of toluene. The residue was dissolved in methanol and boiled with activated carbon. The solution after filtering was evaporated. Yield of adamantane-1-carboxylic acid N-piperidylamide (15) 0.93 g (75%).

b. 40 ml of piperidine was added to 1.05 g of ether (2), boiled for 0.5 h, and treated as indicated above. We obtained 1.7 g of a mixture of substances containing, according to the PMR spectrum, 29% thiol ester (12), 57% piperidinium salt (13), 14% thione ester (2).

Piperidinium salt of adamantane-1-thiolcarboxylic acid (13). 4 ml of absolute acetone was added to the mixture of substances obtained by method *b*. The resulting precipitate was filtered off. Salt yield (13) 0.97 g (69%).

Adamantane-1-thiolcarboxylic acid methyl ester (12). The acetone solution, after isolating salt (13), was evaporated in vacuum. We obtained 0.73 g of residue. Thiol ester (12) was isolated using column chromatography on silica gel, eluent: hexane-ether 5:1 (R_f 0.8). Yield 0.12 g (12%).

Adamantane-1-thiolcarboxylic acid (16). 0.3 g of piperidinium salt of adamantane-1-thiolcarboxylic acid (13) was dissolved in 3 ml of distilled water and acidified with hydrochloric acid. The precipitate that formed was filtered off. Yield 0.21 g (quantitative).

Thermolysis of piperidinium salt of adamantane-1-thiolcarboxylic acid (13) in piperidine. 20 ml of piperidine was added to 0.2 g of salt (13) and boiled for 6 hours. Piperidine was removed in vacuo with the addition of toluene. Yield of N-piperidylamide adamantane-1-carboxylic acid (15) 0.17 g (quantitative).

Thermolysis of piperidinium salt of adamantane-1-thiolcarboxylic acid (13) in N-methylpiperidine was carried out similarly. Yield of N-piperidylamide adamantane-1-carboxylic acid (15) 0.17 g (quantitative).

Detection of N-methylpiperidine in the reaction products of adamantanthione carboxylic acid methyl ester (2) with piperidine. 10 ml of piperidine was added to 0.5 g of thioether (2) and boiled for 0.5 h. The solvent was distilled off at atmospheric pressure, and the residue was washed with acetone. The precipitate that formed was filtered off. We obtained 0.4 g of salt (13). The distillation was analyzed by GLC: piperidine 98.27% (τ 306 s), N-methylpiperidine 1.73%. The content of N-methylpiperidine in the distillate corresponds to the formation of 0.42 g of salt (13).

Interaction of adamantane-1-thiolcarboxylic acid methyl ester (12) with piperidine. To 0.06 g of ether (12) 5 ml of piperidine was added and boiled for 4.5 hours. Piperidine was removed by adding toluene in a vacuum. Yield of the mixture of substances is 0.1 g. PMR spectrum data: 61% thioether (12), 21% salt (13), 18% amide (15).

Interaction of methyl ester of adamantane-1-thionecarboxylic acid (2) with piperidine at different ratios of ester (2) - piperidine. 0.1 g of ether (2) was added to 6 reactors and piperidine was added according to table 3. Boiled for 0.5 hours. Piperidine was removed with the addition of toluene. The residue was analyzed by NMR. The ratio of reaction products is presented in table 3.

Piperidinium salt of adamantane-1-carboxylic acid (17). 30 ml of toluene and 10 ml of piperidine were added to 1.8 g of adamantane-1-carboxylic acid. The solution was left for 24 hours at room temperature. The solvent was distilled off in vacuum. Salt yield (17) 2.65 g (quantitative).

Adamantane-1-carboxylic acid N-piperidylamide (15). To 30 ml of piperidine, while cooling with ice and stirring, 3.97 g of adamantane-1-carboxylic acid chloride was added in portions. Left it overnight. Piperidine was removed in vacuo. 50 ml of 10% hydrochloric acid was added to the residue. The resulting precipitate was filtered off, washed with water, dissolved in 50 ml of methanol and boiled with activated solution. After filtration, the solvent was removed in vacuo. Yield 4.3 g (86%).

Discussion of results.

Usually thionesters are synthesized by the action of esters of carboxylic acids with phosphorus pentasulfide [3, 4]. To do this, use inert, dehydrated solvents such as diethyl ester, benzene, toluene. However, their use failed to obtain the target reaction product (2). During the reaction in dimethoxyethane or dioxane, the highest yield of thionester (2) was achieved by adding 1.5-fold molar excess of P_2S_5 in portions to a solution of boiling adamantane-1-carboxylic acid methyl ester (1) in 6 hours. In dimethoxyethane, the yield did not rise above 69%. In dioxane the yield was 89% in the complete absence of by-products of the reaction.

The reaction was monitored by GC. Thionester (2) was isolated by column chromatography on silica gel. In the IR spectrum of compound (2) there is an absorption band at 1250 cm^{-1} , which corresponds to the valence fluctuations of the $C = S$ bond, and in the PMR spectrum in the region of 3.88 ppm. there is a singlet of protons of the methyl group, shifted by 0.4 ppm in a weak field relative to the original ester (1).

Among the most important chemical properties of thioncarboxylic acid esters are their reactions with diazomethane, which lead to thiazoles and thiadiazolines [5, 6-8], interaction with primary amines, which leads to loss of sulfur function [5] or in the case of hydroxylamine - to thiohydroxy acids [9], reactions with secondary amines, which result in the formation of thioamides [5, 10].

The reaction of the methyl ester of adamantane-1-thioncarboxylic acid (II) with diazomethane was carried out in ether-methanol solution at room temperature

according to the method described in [6]. 5-(1-Adamantyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (3) and 5-(1-adamantyl)-1,2,3-thiadiazole (4) were formed. The reaction products were isolated by column chromatography on silica gel with yields of 32 and 7%, respectively. Characteristic signals [5, 6] of protons of the group $=CH-$ at 8.25 ppm were observed in the PMR spectra of the synthesized compounds. for 1,2,3-thiadiazole (4) and 8.87 ppm for 1,3,4-thiadiazole (3). The shift of the proton signal in the latter case to a weak field is explained, apparently, by the presence of two adjacent heteroatoms (Table 1).

Intermediates in the synthesis of thiadiazoles are thiadiazolines [7]. One of the isomeric thiadiazolines we were able to obtain by reacting thionester (2) with diazomethane in diethyl ether. With a yield of 22%, 5-(1-adamantyl)-5-methoxy-1,2,3-thiadiazoline (5) was isolated, in the PMR spectrum of which methoxyl proton signals (2.81 ppm, singlet) and methylene proton signals were observed. groups at 4.37 and 5.0 ppm, J 20 Hz (Table 1). However, it remained unclear which of the two isomeric thiadiazolines corresponds to the reaction product. This was determined by the decomposition of thiadiazoline (5) in boiling methanol. The formation of 1,2,3-thiadiazole (4) (according to the PMR spectrum) indicates that the parent compound has the structure of 1,2,3-thiadiazoline (5).

As a by-product of the reaction with diazomethane, 1-(1-adamantyl)-1-methoxyethylene (6) is formed, which was isolated only in a mixture with the starting thionester (2). In the PMR spectrum of the mixture, along with the signals corresponding to the initial ester (2), a singlet of protons of the methoxyl group and two doublets at 3.50 and 3.56 ppm, J 2Hz are observed.

The counter-synthesis of compound (6) from 1-adamantylmethyl ketone and orthomuracin ester of the method [11] confirmed the structure of the reaction product.

By analogy with known examples [9], the interaction of thionester (2) with hydroxylamine should form adamantane-1-thionehydroxamic acid. However, the main product of this reaction in methanolic sodium methylate solution was isolated with 71% yield of 1-adamantyl isothiocyanate (7). This is clearly evidenced by the data of the IR spectrum, in which there is a characteristic absorption band at 2100 cm^{-1} , as well as the coincidence of the melting temperature with that indicated in the literature [12].

Table 1

Properties of thionester (2) and products of its interaction with diazomethane

№ Comp.	Yield, %	M.p., °C or n_D^{20}	R_f (eluent)	Spectrum PMR, δ , ppm	IR spectrum, cm^{-1}
2	88	1.5182	0.9(гексан)	1.63 (6H), 1.88(9H), 3.88(3H)	1250, 2800-3000
3	7	34-36	0.4(гексан)	1.5-2.25 (15H), 8.25 (1H)	2800-3000
4	32	137-139	0.75(гексан)	1.5-2.25(15H), 8.87 (1H)	2800-3000
5	22	78-79	-етер)	1.25-2.0(15H), 2.81 (3H), 4.37(1H, J 20Гц), 5.0(1H, J 20Гц)	1210, 1700, 2800-3000
6	83 ^a	(пентан) 1.4983	0.5(гексан -етер) 0.9(гексан -етер)	1.31-2.0(15H), 3.31 (3H), 3.5(1H, J 2 Гц), 3.56(1H, J 2 Гц)	2800-3000

Note. ^a The yield is indicated in the counter-synthesis.

The second reaction product, which was isolated in 29% yield after acidification of the reaction mass, was N-oxyiminomethyl ester of adamantane-1-carboxylic acid (8). In the IR sector of compound (8) there is an absorption band $C=N$ (1670 cm^{-1}), and in the PMR spectrum at 3.88 ppm. and 3.95 ppm - singlets of protons of methyl and hydroxyl groups, respectively.

An additional proof of the structure of the ester (8) is its quantitative conversion under acid hydrolysis to

adamantane-1-carboxylic acid (9) [13]. At the same time, reduction of ester (8) with lithium aluminum hydride leads to 1-adamantylmethylamine (10) [14].

Thus, if the N-hydroxyiminoester (8) is a common reaction product, the migration of the hydrocarbon radical to the nitrogen atom, which leads to isothiocyanate (7), was observed by us in similar transformations for the first time.

Figure 1. General synthesis scheme

The interaction between hydroxylamine and thionester (2), apparently, takes place by the mechanism of attachment of nitrogenous bases to the carbonyl or thiocarbonyl group under alkaline catalysis, thus forming an adduct (A). Sodium hydrosulfide cleavage is sufficient to convert the latter to the iminoester (8). In turn, the elimination of the methanol molecule should lead to thiohydroxamic acid (B). In an alkaline environment, it will exist as a salt, in the molecule of which the excess electron density is distributed between four atoms. It is

logical to assume that devoid of stabilizing effects, for example, aryl substituent [9], salt (B) by cleavage of sodium hydroxide and rearrangement of the Lossen type forms isothiocyanate (7). It remained unclear which of the two hydrogen atoms (hydroxyl or amine) is involved in the elimination of NaSH. To answer this question, we reacted thionester (2) with O-methylhydroxylamine under the same conditions. As a result, the only reaction product was isolated - 1-adamantylcyanide (9).

Figure 2. The mechanism of formation of products (7) and (8).

The synthesis was performed under conditions of prolonged boiling of the reaction mass and controlled by GC. Moreover, depending on the ratio of substrate-reagent (1: 1 or 1: 2) nitrile (9) was obtained with a yield of 49 and 91%, respectively. In the IR spectrum of compound (9), a valence band of the C≡N group is

observed at 2250 cm⁻¹. The melting temperature, IR spectrum data and retention time in GC coincided with similar parameters for the nitrile obtained from adamantane-1-carboxylic acid amide by a known method [15].

Figure 3. The mechanism of formation of product (9)

The first stage of the reaction is apparently the same as with hydroxylamine, and proceeds with the formation of an adduct (A1). The absence of iminoester reaction products indicates that the corresponding direction of reaction is excluded due to the substitution of hydroxyl hydrogen on the methyl group. Then the only possible direction of decomposition of intermediate (A1) is the elimination of methanol and the formation of methyl ester of thionhydroxamic acid (B1). The latter has the possibility of conversion to isothiocyanate, but the lack of promotion of sulfur to the cleavage of methoxyl in the ester (B1), as is the case in intermediate (B), prevents this reaction. In this case, it is possible to interact with the second molecule of O-methylhydroxylamine by one of the variants of the mechanism known for imidoyl halides and related compounds [16], which, apparently, is realized by conversion to amidine (C). The formation of nitrile (9) in the reaction under consideration shows that the substrate in one of the stages

must be reduced. O-methylhydroxylamine should preferably be oxidized. One of the variants of this redox process is a scheme proposed for the conversion of amidine (C) to amidine (D), which is implemented by the type of intramolecular nucleophilic attack on the nitrogen atom [17]. The oxidation product of O-methylhydroxylamine - dimethoxyamine - must be cleaved from intermediate (D). However, without isolating this amine or evidence of its formation, this scheme remains imaginary.

By analogy with the literature [5, 10], the interaction of thionester (2) with secondary amines should lead to the formation of substituted thioamides. However, the first experiments on the interaction of thionester (2) with anhydrous piperidine, taken in large excess, showed the complete absence of N-piperidylamide adamantane-1-thionecarboxylic acid in the reaction products. Instead, after 6 hours of boiling in

amine with a yield of 75% was isolated N-piperidylamide adamantane-1-carboxylic acid (15). In the PMR spectrum of amide (15) in the region of 3.48 ppm there is a multiplet of four protons in the α -position to the nitrogen atom of the piperidine ring. Valence oscillations of the carbonyl group in the IR spectrum are observed in the region of 1610 cm^{-1} . In addition to the spectral characteristics, the melting temperature also coincides with the characteristics of the sample of amide synthesized from adamantane-1-carboxylic acid chloride (table 2).

This unexpected result of the reaction suggests the formation of an intermediate, the decomposition of which leads to the amide (15). We tried to isolate this compound by reducing the synthesis time to 30

minutes. As a result, with a yield of 69%, a water-soluble crystalline compound was isolated, in the PMR spectrum of which proton signals in the range of 9.05 and 3.3.0 ppm are observed. In the IR spectrum, in addition to the valence vibrations of the carbonyl group at 1500 cm^{-1} , which fall into the region of valence vibrations of the C = O group in carboxylate anions [18], an intense band 2200-2700 cm^{-1} was observed, which corresponds to NH valence vibrations in compounds of type $\text{RNH}_2 +$ (table 2). These data suggest that the isolated compound is a piperidine salt of either adamantane-1-carboxylic acid (17) or adamantane-1-thiolcarboxylic acid (13). The choice in favor of compound (13) was made on the basis of comparison of IR and PMR spectra (table 2) of salts (13) and (17). The latter was obtained from adamantane-1-carboxylic acid.

Table 2

Properties of the reaction products of thionester (2) with piperidine				
No Comp.	Yield %	M.p., °C or n_D^{20}	Spectrum PMR, δ , ppm	IR spectrum, cm^{-1}
12	12	1.5286	1.63 (6H), 1.78 (6H), 1.93 (3H), 2.08 (3H)	1600, 2800-3000
13	69	187 (разл.)	1.83-1.58 (21H), 3.0 (4H), 9.05 (2H)	1500, 2200-2700, 2800-3000
15	86	86-87	1.55 (6H), 1.7 (6H), 1.93 (3H) 3.48 (4H)	1605, 2800-3000
16	100	138-140	1.6 (6H), 1.78 (6H), 1.93 (3H), 3.85 (1H)	1680, 2500, 2800-3000
17	100	210 (разл.)	1.60-1.80 (21H), 2.93 (4H), 9.95 (2H)	-

In addition, the acidification of the aqueous salt solution (13) isolated adamantane-1-thiolcarboxylic acid (16), the structure of which was confirmed by IR and PMR spectra (table 2). Prolonged boiling of the salt (13) in the piperidine revealed that the amide (15) is indeed the product of its decomposition.

The second compound formed in the reaction under study, adamantane-1-thiolcarboxylic acid methyl ester (12), was also isolated by column chromatography (yield 31%). Its IR spectrum contains the absorption band of the C = O (1660 cm^{-1}) bond, and the PMR spectrum contains a singlet at 2.08 ppm. (3H), shifted to a strong field compared to esters (1) and (2) by 1.4 and 1.8 ppm, respectively (table 2).

If the thermal rearrangement of thionesters to thioesters is described in the literature [19, 20], the formation of the thiolcarboxylic acid salt was observed by us for the first time. There should be a rupture of the O – CH₃ or S – CH₃ bond and migration of the CH₃ group, and its only acceptor may be piperidine. In other words, the process of salt formation (13) must be accompanied by N-alkylation of piperidine. In the piperidine removed from the reaction mass, N-methylpiperidine was indeed detected by GC (14). Its content in the distillation was equivalent to the amount of salt (13) formed.

Table 3

The effect of excess piperidine on the ratio of salt (13) - thioester (12) ^a	
Excess piperidine relative to the thionester (2), mol	Correlation salt (13) - thioester (12)
20	3.34
40	2.94
80	2.90
160	2.82
320	2.67
640	2.33

Note. ^aThe reaction time is 30 minutes. The data were obtained by integrating the PMR spectrum. The intensities of the corresponding signals of the salt protons (13) and the amide (15) were added.

Thioester (12), like thionester (2), is converted to salt (13) under the reaction conditions, although much more slowly (Table 3). This indicates in favor of the fact that thioester (12) and salt (13) are formed by parallel reactions with thionester (2).

Conclusions.

The study of adamantane-1-carboxylic acid and its derivatives showed that this compound has significant potential for further research in various fields of chemistry and science in general. Adamantane-1-carboxylic

acid is characterized by high structural stability and can be used during the synthesis of various derivatives, for example, esters, amides, and other substances, which opens wide prospects in organic synthesis and some industrial fields. Using the example of the synthesis of methyl ester of adamantane-1-thioncarboxylic acid from P₂S₅, the importance of this method can be emphasized. First, the use of phosphorus pentasulfide as a reagent contributes to a high yield of the product under moderate reaction conditions. Such conditions preserve

the properties and structure of the initial acid, which has an impact on further applications of the obtained product. Secondly, the use of dimethoxyethane or dioxane as a reaction medium allows for good solubility of the reactants and the product, which facilitates the reaction and subsequent purification of the obtained ether. In addition, these reaction media are safe and quite affordable. Thirdly, the synthesis occurs with a high product yield, which indicates the effectiveness and reliability of this method. High product yield is an important factor in large-scale production and in the development of new synthesis approaches.

Analysis of the derived products of methyl ester of adamantane-1-thionecarboxylic acid reveals interesting possibilities and properties of this compound. The structural analysis of the products is confirmed spectrally. The stability of the obtained substances is important for their future use in methods of obtaining biologically active compounds and medicines. According to the fact that the biological activity of adamantane-1-carboxylic acid has promising potential medical applications, the research of its derivatives in the field of medicine and pharmaceuticals may be relevant for further research.

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